

How does research data management actually work?

A guide for chemists and catalyst researchers on digital research data management, repositories and electronic laboratory notebooks

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1. Research data management and the data lifecycle

The term research data management encompasses the entire administration of research data throughout its life cycle, from planning to archiving and reuse.

Research data itself are extremely diverse and include all experiments, measurement data and samples generated in research. The German Research Foundation (DFG) defines research data in its „Checklist for Handling Research Data“ as follows:

„Research data include measurement data, laboratory values, audiovisual information, texts, survey data or observation data, methodological test procedures and questionnaires. Software and simulations can also represent key results of scientific research and are therefore also included under the term research data.“[1]

Figure 1: The life cycle of research data

Planning

When planning a research project and its experiments, a data management plan (DMP) should also be drawn up, which sets out in writing how the following steps in the research data life cycle are to be carried out in practice. The DMP should provide an overview of the type of data collected, the techniques and programmes used to analyse the data, and the plans for publishing and archiving the data. This is particularly important in collaborative projects and third-party funded projects and is often a prerequisite for submitting an application.

(Further information on DMPs can be found in Section 2.)

Collection

Data collection in chemistry is diverse and includes not only experimental parameters such as temperature, time, amounts of substance, volume or concentration, but also experimental observations such as precipitation formation or colour change. All measurements such as NMR, MS, GC, HPLC, IR, Raman, X-ray or other measurements are also data collection, and all these measurements in turn require specific experimental parameters for their execution, such as the spectrometer frequency of the NMR device or the flow rate of the GC or HPLC, to name just a few examples.

Analysis

The measurements taken during data collection provide raw data that must be analysed in some form, usually by a computer programme. For example, NMR spectra or chromatograms from GC and HPLC are analysed by assigning and integrating peaks, while the masses obtained from MS are assigned to the molar masses of the substances or their fragments presumed to be in the sample. The raw data collected previously is thus converted into processed data during analysis. (Further information on research data management and data documentation of collected and analysed data, including recommended digital data management structures and electronic laboratory notebooks, can be found in Section 3.)

Publication

Scientific data are published in publications, presentations or posters. In chemistry, there are usually typical forms of data presentation. Experimental parameters are usually listed in the experimental instructions. In the case of data from measurements, the processed data are usually used in the publication. Data series with a large number of data points, such as a performance data series for a catalyst, are often visualised in diagrams, which is also a form of processed data. (Further information on the publication of data in publications, supporting information, data journals and repositories can be found in Section 5.)

Archiving

Data must be archived to prevent loss and ensure its reuse. In addition to storage on the end user's local computer or on the respective measurement computers, continuous mirroring on a redundant server infrastructure should be carried out in order to eliminate the consequences of data loss without backup. In addition, regular (quarterly to semi-annual) copies of the data can be made on an external hard drive. Generally, data should always be stored in at least two different locations. Further data backups on servers or in cloud services are also recommended, provided these services are available. Finally, there is also the option of using repositories for data archiving, which are often used in connection with publication and are now essential for archiving data in accordance with FAIR principles. Funding bodies such as the DFG often require data to be stored for up to 10 years.

(Further information on data archiving can be found in Section 6.)

Reuse

Science always builds on previous work, and new scientific projects are usually continuations and innovations of old findings. When data is handled correctly throughout its life cycle, it is available for reuse by the next scientist, allowing for a smooth start to the next data cycle.

2. Data management plans

Just as one cannot begin an experiment without prior planning, one should not simply generate data without having a data management plan (DMP) for it. There can be no comprehensive template for a DMP, as it depends on the data generated by the project. The requirements for a DMP depend on the respective funding institution and the type of project. In its „Checklist for Handling Research Data“, the DFG formulates some key questions for creating a DMP:[1]

1. How are new data generated in your project? What types of data are generated and how are they processed?
2. What measures are taken to ensure high data quality? Are quality controls planned and, if so, how? What digital methods and tools (e.g. software) are required to use the data?
3. How will the data be stored and backed up during the project?
4. What are the specific legal issues relating to the handling of research data in your project? Are there any expected implications or restrictions regarding subsequent publication or accessibility?
5. Which data is particularly suitable for reuse in other contexts? Do you plan to archive your data in a suitable infrastructure?
6. Who is responsible for the proper handling of research data? Who is responsible for curating the data after the end of the project?

These key questions show that, in the broadest sense, a DMP covers all steps of the data life cycle and at the same time defines responsibility for the handling of research data. While the main responsibility for drafting and maintaining the DMP itself usually lies with the research leader, DMPs and institutional guidelines generally stipulate that each researcher is responsible for ensuring that the data is available in a usable format.

It should be borne in mind that a DMP may change during a project. Just as experiments can lead to unexpected results, data other than that originally planned may be generated, or there may be changes in the software used. For example, unplanned new findings may arise along the scientific project, which in turn may lead to new measurements and thus new measurement data. One example of this would be the investigation of the surface of a catalyst to understand its deactivation during the reaction.

The following chapters contain descriptions and tips on how to handle research data digitally, from its collection to its archiving in the context of chemistry and catalysis.

3. Traditional laboratory notebook or digital FDM?

Whether you are an intern, a bachelor's or master's student, a doctoral candidate or a postdoc: when working in the laboratory, the data collected must be recorded as directly as possible. The DFG writes the following in its „Guidelines for Ensuring Good Scientific Practice“:

„Continuous quality assurance throughout the research process refers in particular to compliance with subject-specific standards [...] and to the keeping of laboratory notebooks“[2]

Over the last few centuries, laboratory notebooks have been kept in analogue and paper-based form. This is still common practice at many research institutions, as paper-based laboratory notebooks are easy to use and inexpensive.

Figure 2: A typical laboratory notebook from chemistry

Despite their practical value and quick handling for data collection, paper-based laboratory notebooks are no longer up to date. The steps in research data management that follow data collection, especially the analysis and publication of data, are always carried out digitally. This results in the additional effort of first transferring the analogue data into a digital format, for example into a text document or data table, before it can be further used and evaluated.

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Figure 3: Example of local digital research data management

1) The naming and structure of the folders should be clear and consistent. The specific naming is of course freely selectable, but it is important that the content is also visible to subsequent users from the folder. Avoid nesting too many folders. Due to the limitations of some operating systems, such as Windows, the names of folders and files should not contain more than 25 characters or any special characters.

In the example given, the folders were named using the abbreviation used in the laboratory for the reaction, a sequential catalyst number and a short, concise description of the catalyst.

2) All data relating to a catalyst is stored in the folder for that catalyst. This data should be named in a way that directly reflects its content and makes it easy to find using search functions.

In the example given, the Cat 5 folder contains the raw NMR data, the processed NMR data and the images created from it, the ESI-MS measurement, the TGA measurement and a test procedure with a description of the synthesis of the catalyst. The data on the application of the catalyst in a test reaction is also stored here. The abbreviation is used in all file names to make it easy to assign the files to the correct catalyst. Of course, it should be easy for a user to find out where more detailed information relating to the abbreviation can be found, e.g. the composition of the catalyst. A corresponding list should be attached to the data set or at least clearly linked.

3) Finally, all performance data obtained for the catalysts after their use in a test reaction was compiled in a csv file and plotted in a data diagram.

Things become more complex when, beyond standard „wet chemistry“ laboratory work, complex equipment and corresponding reaction technology are used, particularly in catalysis research. This equipment is often individually designed and constructed or purchased as a complete system from the relevant manufacturers. In any case, they are very individually tailored to the respective research question and always consist of a variety of different components (e.g. mass flow controllers, pumps, reactors, heating/cooling elements, pressure reducers, back pressure regulators, online or in situ analytics). In order to ensure complete reproducibility, it is essential to comprehensively document the relevant metadata for the system and all variable or recorded test parameters. This includes, in particular, the chronological tracking of information on the replacement of individual components or changes in the configuration of the system, so that experiments carried out at any time and their data can be reconciled with the current state of the system and the data can ultimately be archived with the correct and complete metadata or published as research data in repositories.

Whether in a traditional laboratory notebook or in a separate digital structure, it is important that all data is available with rich metadata documentation. Above all, the following points should be findable in some form in research data management:

- Who recorded the data/conducted the experiment?
- When was the experiment conducted?
- Where was the experiment conducted?
- What was carried out?
- Why was it carried out?
- How was it carried out?

The key questions „Where, why and how?“ do not necessarily have to be documented for each individual experiment, as in practice a series of similar experiments with the same procedure and purpose, but with individually different parameters, often contribute to a larger overall goal. If the documentation is not complete for all individual data, it must still be clear where the relevant information can be found.

4. Examples of digital FDM with eLabFTW

Digital research data management, as shown in Figure 3 in the previous chapter, can take place locally on each end user's own computer. With good data management, this data can be used as a basis for bachelor's, master's or doctoral theses, and these data and folder structures can also be handed over to the scientific supervisor, for example for archiving or reuse.

Electronic lab notebooks, often referred to as ELNs, are a modern solution that offers all aspects of data collection, research data management, archiving and reuse in one place. There are numerous different ELNs available, which differ in their basic functions and subject focus. A helpful overview of ELNs can be found at ELN Finder[3]. When selecting an ELN, in addition to its basic functions and subject focus, the following criteria should be considered:

- Licence model: Commercial ELNs have licence fees but also offer a corresponding service. Open-source ELNs are free of charge and can be further developed independently but must also be implemented and maintained independently. However, support is often offered for open-source ELNs for a fee.
- File formats: Is the ELN compatible with common file formats? Does it allow the import and export of data in these common file formats (e.g. pdf, xls, rtf, csv)?
- Deployment model: Does the ELN run on a local server or in the cloud?
- Interfaces: Does the ELN allow data exchange with external programmes, such as ChemDraw?
- Is it possible to create templates to speed up the work process?
- Are there functions for individually defining the write and read permissions for entries within the ELN?
- Verifiability: Can changes to entries in the ELN be tracked using timestamps or versions?
- Exit plan: Not all software can be assumed to be available indefinitely. Sometimes developments in a project, such as collaboration with a new partner, require a switch to a different ELN. To ensure that this works, it should be possible to export entries in a common format so that importing them into another ELN is as easy as possible later on.

From the perspective of an individual user, it should be noted that many ELNs are specifically designed for group use and, in addition to the function of experiment recording, also include numerous other laboratory management functions. The decision to use an ELN is therefore usually made for the entire working group, the entire university or the entire company.

In this guide, we present the use of ELNs for research data management and advanced workgroup management using eLabFTW as an example. The ELN eLabFTW is a subject-independent open source ELN that is hosted on a local server and can then be used by any registered user via an internet browser. Individual use is possible in the case of eLabFTW.

The screenshot displays the 'Experiments' overview in eLabFTW. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'EXPERIMENTS' selected. Below it, the 'Experiments' title is followed by a 'Create' button. A table lists three experiments with columns for Date, Title, Next step, Category, Status, and Tags. A 'Scope' dropdown menu is open, showing options for 'Self', 'Team', and 'Everything'. Arrows point to various UI elements: 1) points to the 'Create' button, 2) points to the 'Experiments' header, 3) points to the 'Create' button, 4) points to the 'Status' column, 5) points to the 'Scope' dropdown, and 6) points to the 'Filters' dropdown.

Date	Title	Next step	Category	Status	Tags
2025-04-25	SJ183 - Acetal deprotection		SYNTHESIS	PLANNING	
2025-04-25	SJ182 - Benzylolation of Methyl glucopyranoside		SYNTHESIS	SUCCESS	
2024-10-14	SJ181 - Kolbe 40°C, 8h, 2.0eq NaCN		CATALYSIS	SUCCESS	Kolbe nitrile synthesis

Figure 4: Experiment overview in eLabFTW

1) In addition to basic UI (user interface) settings, templates can also be managed in your own profile. The entire profile (including all settings and experiments) can also be imported or exported in various file formats. It is also possible to export individual or selected experiments (see Fig. 5).

2) The experiment page in eLabFTW (Fig. 4) contains an overview of all experiments that have been entered in the electronic lab book. The experiments displayed can be restricted to different persons or different search criteria depending on the filter (see points 5 and 6).

3) New experiments can be created using the Create button. Experiments are created in a text editor (see Fig. 5), where templates can also be created and saved, which can be accessed via the Create button.

4) For easy classification, experiments can be sorted into categories and tagged, which can also be used for searching. The categories are defined by the working group leader or other administrators. Tags can be created independently by each user. The naming of tags should be consistent and scientifically comprehensible. In addition, the status of the experiment can also be recorded in different stages, for example, planning, ongoing, failure or success.

5) In eLabFTW, scientists in a working group can view each other's experiments if they wish. In this case, under Scope, the view of the experiments can be set to the user themselves, a defined team, or the entire working group.

6) Experiments can be filtered by category, status or tag.

eLabFTW EXPERIMENTS RESOURCES TEAM SEARCH SHAREPOINT

SJ182 - Benzylation of Methyl glucopyranoside Create

← 1)

Started on 2025-04-25
 Team AG Kragl
 Category **SYNTHESIS**
 Status **SUCCESS**
 # ID 6922

5) →

- Transfer ownership
- See revisions
- See changelog
- Archive/Unarchive
- Delete

Visibility + Only members of the team ← 2)
 Can write + Only owner and admins

MAIN TEXT

Used Chemicals

Name or Abbreviation	mmol	equivalents	amount
Methyl α-D-glucopyranoside	25		4.852 g
DMF			100 mL
NaH on paraffine (60%)	200	8 (2.0 per OH group)	7.997 g
Benzyl bromide	200	8 (2.0 per OH group)	23.7 mL

Product:

- M = 554.68 g/mol
- 100% yield = 13.867 g

Reaction Procedure:

- dissolve methyl α-D-glucopyranoside in DMF (250 mL flask) and cool to 0 °C
- add NaH portionwise over 5 min
- add benzyl bromide
- allow reaction to warm to room temperature and stir overnight
- Start of reaction (after addition of BnBr): 29.07.24, 13:30
- End of reaction: 30.07.24, 9:30 --> 20h reaction time
- remove DMF as much as possible at rotary evaporator (water bath up to 70°C) ← 3)
- add 100 mL water
- extract with 2x 100 mL DCM
- dry organic phase over Na₂SO₄
- column chromatography heptane/EE 9:1
- m = 15.063 g, colourless oil/ liquid, 108% yield (solvent remaining, NMR otherwise clean)

NMR:
240801.503

Owner: Stefan Jopp
 Last modified on 2025-04-25 10:45:53
 Unique eLabID: 20250425-d5f565a60fd52d6ff25fce0428f7d83c838846b8

LINKED EXPERIMENTS (1)

SYNTHESIS PLANNING SJ183 - Acetal deprotection ← 4)

ATTACHED FILES (3)

SJ182-Reaction-Scheme.png 25.11 KIB - 2025-04-25 10:44:48
Click to add a comment

SJ182-NMR-1H.png 83.34 KIB - 2025-04-25 10:39:43
Click to add a comment

SJ182-NMR-13C.png 75.59 KIB - 2025-04-25 10:39:43
Click to add a comment

Figure 5: View of an experiment in eLabFTW

1) In the entry for an experiment in eLabFTW (Fig. 5), it is possible to export it. An export in pdf or csv format only includes the main text field. It is possible to specify whether the changelog (change history of the experiment) should also be included in the pdf file. It is also possible to export an experiment in eln format. All metadata (such as linked experiments) and attached data are retained. The eln format can be used to transfer experiments between different instances of eLabFTW. Some other ELN providers also support the eln format but depending on the individual functions of the different ELNs, complete data transfer between them cannot be guaranteed.

2) The visibility and write permissions of an experiment can be configured individually. This means that experiments can be made visible and editable only to the user themselves or to a defined group of users, for example, if this is necessary for an industrial collaboration.

3) The main text field corresponds to an entry in the laboratory notebook and can be customised using a text editor. It is also possible to insert image files directly into the main text field. Below the main text field, additional fields for meta-data and a manual checklist can be created to track the individual steps of the synthesis or characterisation of a catalyst with recorded times (not shown here).

4) An experiment in eLabFTW can be linked to one or more other experiments or resources. It is also possible to attach any number of files in any file format to the experiment. This allows all data for an experiment or for a specific sample to be stored in one place.

5) Changes to the experiment entry can be tracked. It is possible to delete the entry, but depending on the admin's settings, this may not be permanent.

Date	Title	Next step	Category	Status	Tags	Rating	Owner
<input type="checkbox"/> 2025-03-26	GC-MS method_sugars_organic acids		METHOD	AVAILABLE	Analytics GC/MS Sugar		
<input type="checkbox"/> 2025-01-16	Betriebsanweisung GC		METHOD	AVAILABLE			
<input type="checkbox"/> 2025-01-15	Device Log GC Trace 1310 (rechts)		DEVICE LOG	AVAILABLE	Analytics Device GC Trace		
<input type="checkbox"/> 2025-01-15	GC Trace 1310 (rechts)		DEVICE	AVAILABLE	Analytics Device GC Trace		

Figure 6: Resources in eLabFTW

The resource page (Fig. 6) in eLabFTW does not have a predetermined content. Here, each working group can decide individually which additional resources should be stored. As shown in Figure 6, these can be methods, devices and device logbooks, for example. However, a list of chemicals or other materials are also conceivable on the resource page. The entries stored in the resources can also be linked to experiments. For example, a direct link to the device, method or chemicals used can be made in the experiments.

It is also possible to set devices on the resources page as bookable. In this case, a schedule with the planned usage times for each device can be viewed on the eLabFTW team page.

5. Publication: Supporting information, data journals, repositories and FAIR data

Good data management is a prerequisite for good publication. At the same time, publications, at least in the actual scientific articles, usually only list and discuss processed data, for example in data tables or diagrams.

In the supporting information, which is an additional file available online alongside the publication, authors can and should store all data that substantiates and supports the publication. However, since SI is usually in the form of text documents or xls documents, difficulties arise: raw data from measurements such as MS, NMR or X-ray cannot be listed in such SI because they are based on their own file formats. For this reason, SIs often list figures or data tables that reflect these measurements. However, this compromise means that other scientists do not have access to the raw data, which often leads to problems with the reproducibility of the data. Furthermore, this means that the data is not machine-readable for automated data analysis or machine learning programmes.

In recent years, two other options for data publication have therefore become established: data journals and repositories.

Data journals are scientific journals in which data can be published. Just like other scientific publications, they are subject to a peer review process and publication costs. Unlike other scientific publications, data articles in data journals merely describe the data obtained in detail and do not have to provide new insights. They therefore represent a high-quality alternative to data publication and can also be cited by other scientific articles. However, the use of data journals in chemistry has hardly become established to date.

Repositories are databases for storing, archiving and sharing digital data. Many repositories are free of charge and do not have a peer review process. Repositories enable both the findability and accessibility of data (cf. FAIR, Fig. 7) and its long-term archiving. Repositories usually offer persistent identifiers (PIDs), such as DOIs (digital object identifiers), which are widely used in the scientific community. This allows the data uploaded to the repository to be cited and linked to other scientific publications. The most important difference between a PID and a simple link is that links can change, e.g. when a website changes its name. Although the repository operator would still be responsible for ensuring that the associated data remains available in such a case, the PID makes it possible to always find the data unambiguously, even if the storage location or link changes. A carefully described dataset in a repository can often replace the need to describe the same dataset in the SI. Thus, the use of a repository often saves time in the publication process while providing other scientists with access to the raw data. In addition, scientists can search for and find the data in the repository even if they are not familiar with the associated publication. The following repositories are recommended for the typical data generated in the fields of chemistry and catalysis:

- re3data:[4] Provides an overview of repositories from all subject areas.
- Zenodo:[5] A multidisciplinary repository developed by CERN that allows easy data upload from any data format and makes the data sets findable via DOI.
- Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC):[6] A repository for crystal data in cif file format.
- NMR Archive (nmrXiv):[7] A repository specifically for NMR data from molecules.
- MassBank:[8] A database for MS data.
- Repo4Cat:[9] A repository developed by NFDI4Cat for uploading data sets from the field of catalyst development and application, which uses handles instead of DOIs as PIDs. Handles function in the same way as a DOI. However, due to their different structure, it is possible to assign handles to devices and individual samples to make them uniquely identifiable.
- RADAR4Chem:[10] A repository developed by NFDI4Chem for chemistry-specific datasets.
- NOMAD:[11] A repository for datasets from the field of materials science. NOMAD also has a section on data from heterogeneous catalysis and offers tools for visualising the data.

While repositories such as CCDC or nmrXiv specialise in specific file formats and can also read these file formats automatically, in open repositories such as Zenodo it is important to upload the data sets in a comprehensible structure and to use reusable data formats such as csv or rtf. It is recommended to create a digital data structure as shown in Figure 3 and to describe any abbreviations used in an additional „Readme“ text file. Further recommendations for publishing data in repositories can be found in the „Guideline for Open Data Publishing“.[1,2]

Whether SI, data journal or repository: in all cases, data in science should be as accessible and as well described as possible in order to promote the reproduction of scientific experiments and global scientific progress. In this sense, the acronym FAIR (Fig. 7) has become particularly well established.[13] FAIR means that, first, a dataset should be findable through a clear description of its content using metadata. Second, permanent access to the dataset should be ensured. This can include both open access (open data) and restricted access via authentication. Thirdly, the data should be available in a general format that is compatible with many programmes. Fourthly, the data should be in an understandable and comprehensively documented state that guarantees its reusability.

Figure 7: FAIR Data

6. About data archiving

Archiving data sustainably is not only important for preserving its scientific value in the long term and making research results traceable but is also required by the guidelines of projects and institutions.

Data loss is unpredictable and should always be taken into account as a risk. Whether the research data is stored in a traditional laboratory notebook or digitally on your own computer, a spilled drink, damage to the computer or, in worse cases, a fire can suddenly and unexpectedly lead to the loss of all research data.

For this reason, the following minimum requirements for data backup must be observed: Research data should be copied regularly (the more frequently the better, realistically once a month is recommended) to a second medium, for example from your own computer to an external hard drive. This second medium should be physically stored in a different location from the first medium. A third copy in secure online storage is also recommended. Nowadays, however, permanent backup via mirroring on at least one server at a different location should be the norm, ideally redundant, in order to completely rule out absolute data loss. Such a backup should also be fully automated so that there is no dependence on human users.

The archived data should be available in a structure and quality that allows for its reuse. In addition to clear folder structures and file names (see Fig. 3), the file formats and their usability with typical programmes in the field must also be taken into account.

It is also important to note that, according to the DFG's „Guidelines for Handling Research Data“, data should be archived for at least 10 years. [14]

In the previous chapters, ELNs such as eLabFTW were discussed in the context of research data management, and repositories were discussed in the context of data publication. These applications and services usually also involve data archiving and are therefore also recommended for data archiving purposes, especially since the functions of the respective service must be considered individually.

7. Take-home messages

Whether you use a traditional laboratory notebook and file your data as printouts, structure your data digitally yourself, or use an ELN, research data management is a natural part of research.

However, not all students and scientists are clear from the outset about which form of research data management suits them best and at the same time complies with external requirements.

This guide therefore explains each step of the data life cycle with practical examples and tips for implementing digital research data management, including suggestions for digital data structures and an introduction to ELNs and repositories. The most important thing to note here is that all data should be stored in an easily comprehensible naming convention and structure and in file formats that can be used in the long term. Here, you can ask yourself the question: „Have I described my data well enough that I will be able to understand everything myself later on?“ The first user of good research data management is always the researcher themselves.

To make a positive contribution to the future reproducibility of scientific experiments, use repositories to upload raw data to accompany your publication.

And in the end, any form of digital FDM is better than no FDM at all.

8. References

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- [6] Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC): <https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/>
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- [8] MassBank: <https://massbank.eu/MassBank/>
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Notes

nfdi4cat.org

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